

POULTRY BUILDINGS FOR CREATED THE AIR COOLING EQUIPMENT TO POULTRY PRODUCTIVITY EFFECT EVALUATION

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Abstract. Poultry optimal conditions in buildings create and created microclimate under the influence of poultry health and productivity significant level to increase achieved. In this case, from vermiculite from the material prepared the air cooling from the equipment when used, traditional cooling equipment relatively of poultry productivity 65690 units to 73369 units to increase achieved.

Keywords: vermiculite, nozzle, productivity, intensity, traditional cooling.

Optimum air in poultry houses parameters Creating and improving the plan of measures to increase the productivity of poultry and providing poultry houses with modern, energy-efficient facilities is an urgent problem of today's poultry buildings is coming. Because some of the poultry houses used today are using only ventilators to improve the relative humidity and temperature parameters of the air. It is important to provide such poultry buildings with evaporative air cooling systems when evaluating economic performance indicators.

After clarifying the results of the analysis of the energy consumption of high-energy and conventional equipment to ensure microclimate parameters in poultry buildings, we will also consider the effect of poultry on egg productivity.

There is also a change in the share of the products obtained depending on the efficiency of the water vapor cooling systems used in the poultry houses and the efficiency of the created energy-saving systems. Taking into account the difference between these amounts, we calculate the intensity of energy in relation to the produced product. Intensity below in the calculation given from the formula we use

$$N_{inte.k} = \frac{E}{Q}$$

in which:

General electricity of electronic devices energy consumption , (kW). When determining this value, as we mentioned above, we take into account the amount of electricity consumed for the operation of fans that provide air movement in the building. Eight suction fans are installed in the poultry house, and the electricity consumption is 0.5 kW. The power of electric energy consumed in the hot season of the year for common ventilators is 4500 kW.

In research poultry houses, birds are kept for obtaining eggs. Therefore, we take into account the egg production of poultry as an output. In practice, the productivity of poultry in a poultry building equipped with a ventilation system $Q_{ama.mav}$ =is 65,690 units per day.

We can see that the daily egg production of the next birds equipped with vermiculite nozzles increased by $Q_{established}$ 73369 eggs.

$$N_{fos.nas}^{int} = \frac{E}{Q_{fos.cand}} = \frac{460}{65690} = 0,0070$$

$$N_{established}^{int} = \frac{E}{Q_{established}} = \frac{460}{73369} = 0,0062$$

Farming in progress in the building After installing the air cooling equipment made of vermiculite material, we will look at the total cost savings:

$$S_{tej} = \left(\frac{X_{year}^{fossil}}{Q_{fossil}} - \frac{X_{year}^{established}}{Q_{established}} \right) * Q_{established},$$

in this

$X_{year}^{established}, X_{year}^{established}$ –Costs of existing and proposed microclimate maintenance facilities in the poultry house, (soums).

$Q_{fossil}, Q_{established}$ –Effect of conventional and proposed microclimatic equipment on egg production and productivity index, (pieces).

$$E_i = \left(\frac{18264700}{65690} - \frac{13288700}{73369} \right) * 73369 = 7\ 116\ 793\ \text{soum}$$

After the installation of the proposed energy-saving microclimate installation in the poultry house, we determine the economic efficiency through the following formula for the hot season.

$$E = (P_{established} - I_{established}) - (P_{fossil} - I_{fossil})$$

in this

P_n, P_b –total productivity value in poultry houses as a result of conventional and proposed equipment. In this case, we consider the price of one egg produced today as 1,000 soums.

$$P_n = 73369 * 1000 = 73369000\ \text{so'm}$$

$$P_b = 65690 * 1000 = 65690000\ \text{so'm}$$

Taking into account the effectiveness of increasing egg productivity in poultry buildings, the use of evaporative vermiculite cooling equipment is based on increasing the productivity of poultry and maintaining the microclimate in the building by saving electricity.

$$E = (73369000 - 13\ 288700) - (65690000 - 18\ 264700) = 12655000\ \text{so'm}$$

Economic efficiency in the amount of 12655000 soums was achieved after the installation of the energy-saving equipment created in order to reduce the share of electricity used to create microclimate parameters in poultry buildings and increase productivity. In addition, after the installation of energy-efficient equipment in the poultry house, a significant change in the health of the poultry was achieved.

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